

Highlights

Dispatch and Sizing Optimization of Molten-Salt Power-to-Heat Systems for Industrial Heat Decarbonization in Balancing Electricity Markets

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- First techno-economic assessment of P2H+TES in balancing markets for industrial steam
- Balancing market participation reduces LCOH by >65% vs DAM-only operation
- Operational cost savings of 0.9–1.9 M€/y vs electric boilers
- Impact of electricity network charges on economics and sizing is non-negligible
- Optimal TES storage-to-power ratio of 2–4 h consistent across scenarios and markets

Dispatch and Sizing Optimization of Molten-Salt Power-to-Heat Systems for Industrial Heat Decarbonization in Balancing Electricity Markets

Pavla Lukášová^{a,*}, Adam Kubín^a and Radek Procházka^a

^aFaculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Technická 1902/2, Praha 6, 166 27, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Decarbonization of industry remains one of the most significant challenges in the energy transition. Industrial process heat presents a particularly hard-to-abate source of emissions, as it continues to depend on fossil fuels. To address this challenge, the presented work investigates a power-to-heat (P2H) system integrated with molten-salt thermal energy storage (TES) for medium-temperature industrial steam generation. A techno-economic assessment is conducted, with a focus on dispatch optimization under dynamic electricity pricing, including day-ahead markets as well as ancillary services markets in Czech Republic and Germany. The system is modeled using a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) algorithm. Multiple system configurations are then evaluated to identify the most cost-effective sizing strategy based on the Levelized Cost of Heat. To assess the demand-side flexibility benefits provided by TES, the proposed P2H+TES system was benchmarked against a conventional P2H system, represented by an electric boiler. The results show that participation in balancing markets substantially improves economic performance, reducing the LCOH of 131 €/MWh in the DAM-only scenario by more than 65 % for the optimally sized configuration. Compared to an electric boiler, the proposed system achieves operational cost savings of 0.9–1.9 M€/y when aFRR-services are included. Despite growing interest in industrial P2H systems with TES, the scientific literature on their use for process steam supply remains limited. This study provides the first techno-economic assessment combining dispatch strategies in day-ahead and ancillary services markets, highlighting both economic benefits and the potential to support industrial decarbonization.

1. Introduction

Industrial decarbonization represents a key challenge on the path toward climate neutrality. The industrial sector remains heavily reliant on fossil fuels [1], with renewable energy sources contributing only 14 % to its final energy consumption [2]. Globally, the industrial sector represents 38% of total final energy consumption and 47 % of CO₂ emissions (including not only process emissions, but also emissions from electricity and heat), making it the largest end-use sector for both energy demand and greenhouse gas emissions [1].

The majority of energy consumed in the industrial sector is used for process heat production [2]. Industrial processes require heat at varying temperature levels. In general, the process heat can be categorized as low-temperature heat (below 150 °C), medium-temperature heat (150–400 °C), high-temperature heat (400 °C - 1000 °C) and very high-temperature heat (above 1000 °C) [2]. The wide range of industrial processes complicates decarbonization efforts, as no single universal solution can effectively address all industrial heat demand. [3].

Low-temperature heat is typically required in textile, chemical or food industry. Paper industry, along with food production, use medium-temperature heat. High-temperature process heat is requested by the chemical, minerals and steel industry [4, 5]. Low-temperature heat can be produced

by a variety of low-emission technologies, such as heat pumps, but sustainable pathways for generating medium- and high-temperature heat remain limited [6]. At the same time, the majority of industrial heat consumption in EU is concentrated at medium- and high-temperature levels [4, 7]. This mismatch between technological availability and industrial demand highlights the urgency of developing alternative solutions.

One of the key strategies to address this challenge and reduce greenhouse gas emissions in industry is the electrification of process heat [3, 8, 9, 10]. This strategy focuses on generating heat with low-carbon electricity as an alternative to fossil fuels. The electrification of heat can be achieved through power-to-heat (P2H) technologies, which involve the conversion of electrical energy into heat. Examples of such technologies include electric boilers, heat pumps, as well as resistance, induction, infrared and microwave heating methods, electric arc furnaces or plasma torches [4, 11]. P2H technologies are capable of meeting all industrial heat demand across all temperature levels [11].

Thermal energy storage (TES) can effectively complement P2H by providing flexibility in thermal energy management. By integrating TES, industries can adjust to fluctuating electricity prices and still produce heat on demand [4, 12]. By choosing an appropriate storage material, TES systems can be designed to store and deliver heat at temperatures that match specific industrial requirements. This adaptability allows TES systems to meet a wide range of industrial heat demands. The most widely deployed and commercially mature TES systems are based on sensible

*Corresponding author

 pavla.lukasova@fel.cvut.cz (P. Lukášová)
ORCID(s): 0009-0000-6945-6821 (P. Lukášová)

heat storage mechanism. These systems raise, resp. lower, the temperature of the storage material to store, resp. release, heat. Common storage materials include liquids such as water, thermal oils, and molten salts, as well as solids including rocks, concrete, sand, and ceramics. The applications range from residential low-temperature water tanks to high-temperature molten-salt storage for concentrated solar power (CSP) plants with capacity on the GWh scale [13]. Other TES concepts, based on latent or thermochemical heat storage, remain at earlier stage of development with further R&D efforts needed for scaling up [14, 15].

P2H technologies are widely recognized as a key strategy to enhance the integration of variable renewable energy sources [16, 17]. TES represents a significant addition to P2H technologies, enhancing flexibility [16]. This hybrid P2H+TES system, provides demand-side flexibility (load shifting) and contributes to grid stability. Moreover, the integration of TES allows operators to participate in ancillary services markets, providing opportunities for additional revenue streams [18].

A large volume of literature has examined P2H technologies, but most research has concentrated on low-temperature heat generation, primarily targeting residential and district heating systems. For this reason, most studies examine heat pumps and electric boilers as the principal P2H technologies, and when TES is considered, it is typically limited to low-temperature systems such as water tanks [19, 20, 21, 22].

Several studies addressed the application of P2H technologies in the industrial sector. Electrification of process heat via P2H technologies was proposed among strategies to decarbonize many industry sub-sectors, such as pulp and paper industry [23], food and beverage industry [24], chemical industry [5, 25, 26], steel industry [5, 27], ceramics industry [28] or glass industry [29]. Madeddu et al. performed a comprehensive bottom-up analysis to estimate the potential of heat electrification in European industry as a measure for CO₂ emissions reduction. The results indicate that 78 % of energy demand in European industry can be electrified via well-established technologies. Emerging technologies that are still under development can enable up to 99% electrification in the future [11]. The growing interest of TES application in industry is well documented in [14]. In this paper, Pantaleo et al. overviewed start-ups providing medium- and high-temperature solutions and concluded that sensible heat storage systems are the most developed, with some systems ready for deployment at industrial scale [14]. In addition, successful operation of a pilot molten-salt TES unit equipped with an electric heater, supplying heat to a district heating network in Denmark, was reported in [30]. This paper also highlights the potential of the P2H system to participate in flexibility markets, thanks to fast activation time demonstrated by the experimental data.

However, there has been limited research on the techno-economic evaluation of P2H systems coupled with TES for medium- and high-temperature process heat generation [12, 31, 32]. Mahmoudinezhad et al. investigated a P2H system

integrated with molten-salt TES for industrial steam supply. The study underscored the importance of further research, particularly operation under dynamic electricity price profiles, as their work assumed constant electricity prices [31]. In contrast, Hamilton et al. explicitly addressed the role of electricity price variability by developing a dispatch optimization model for a power-to-heat-to-power configuration. Their system combined an electrical heater, molten-salt TES, and a steam cycle, and was operated in a day-ahead electricity market. They demonstrated that financial viability is strongly dependent on optimal dispatch decisions, achieving up to a 20% increase in revenues compared to heuristic dispatch strategies thanks to their mixed-integer linear program (MILP) optimization model [33]. Similarly, Trevisan et al. performed a comprehensive MILP-based optimization of the dispatching and sizing of a P2H system coupled with TES for delivering process steam. The study concluded that the investigated system could lower operational expenses by 0.5 to 3 M€/y compared to conventional electric boilers, achieving even higher savings in comparison to fossil fuel boilers [32].

In summary, the literature overview revealed a clear gap in studies investigating P2H systems integrated with TES for medium- and high-temperature industrial heat supply. Techno-economic analyses of such systems, particularly in real industrial contexts, remain scarce. Thus, further investigation is required to enhance understanding and support industrial-scale implementation. This work builds on and extends the analysis presented in [32] by evaluating the system's potential to provide flexibility in balancing markets. To the best of our knowledge, no study has yet examined industrial molten salt-based P2H systems providing ancillary services through a techno-economic model with dispatch optimization. This highlights the novelty of the present work for both research and practical implementation. Furthermore, our work accounts for the full electricity cost structure, including not only the energy commodity component but also regulated network tariffs, which have a significant impact on the techno-economic viability of electricity storage systems but are often neglected in the literature.

In this paper, a techno-economic analysis is conducted to assess the performance and feasibility of a molten salt-based P2H system for industrial heat supply. At the core of the study is a MILP algorithm developed to optimize the dispatch of the system in dynamic electricity markets, including not only the day-ahead market, but also the ancillary services market. Various system configurations are evaluated to determine the most cost-effective sizing strategy, using the Levelized Cost of Heat as the performance metric. Finally, the developed methodology is applied to a real-world case study of an industrial plant, and the results are benchmarked against conventional industrial heat generation technologies, namely an electric boiler.

Figure 1: Layout of the proposed TES-integrated P2H system

2. System description

A block diagram of the investigated P2H system with high-temperature TES (P2H+TES) is shown in Fig. 1. The system can be divided into three basic functional units: P2H system, TES system, and the Steam Generation System (SGS).

Table 1
YARA MOST thermophysical properties [34]

Parameter	Unit	Value
Composition	[wt %]	KNO_3 - NaNO_3 - CaNO_3 [43 - 15 - 42]
Freezing temperature	[°C]	131
Max. operating temp.	[°C]	500
Specific heat (@ 300 °C)	[J/kg K]	1530
Density (@ 300 °C)	[kg/m ³]	1986
Thermal conductivity	[W/m K]	0.55

The proposed TES system is based on a two-tank configuration, typically used at CSPs, consisting of hot and cold storage tanks and utilizing molten salt (MS) as the heat transfer and storage medium. The most commonly used material for medium- and high-temperature heat storage is solar salt, a binary mixture of NaNO_3 and KNO_3 , which has been widely employed in CSP plants. However, due to its high freezing point (around 230 °C), solar salt is unsuitable for heat generation systems operating below this threshold, which covers a substantial share of industrial thermal demands. Lower operating temperatures can be achieved with ternary salt mixtures. The proposed TES system utilizes Yara MOST (trade name), a ternary salt mixture based on potassium nitrate (KNO_3), sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) and calcium nitrate (CaNO_3). The operational range of MS is defined by its freezing point and maximum allowable temperature, which is limited by thermal decomposition. The thermophysical properties of YARA MOST are detailed in Table 1. To compensate for heat losses and to prevent salt freezing, the storage tanks are typically equipped with additional electric heating. The circulation of MS is ensured by pumps.

The P2H conversion is performed by a resistance electric heater (EH), which consists of multiple heating rods inserted

within a shell. Multiple EH units can be used to speed up the charging process and take advantage of times with negative electricity prices.

The final key component of the proposed system is the steam generation system, which includes a series of heat exchangers transferring heat between molten salt and water/steam. In the proposed SGS, an economizer followed by an evaporator is considered. However, if superheated steam is required by the customer, a superheater can be added to the system.

The proposed system can operate in multiple modes. In charging mode, the cold MS passes through the EH, where it is heated and subsequently stored in the hot tank. During the discharging, hot MS is circulated through a series of heat exchangers in the SGS to transfer thermal energy to water, producing steam for industrial processes. The cooled MS returns to the cold tank. The proposed system also enables simultaneous charging & discharging. Another possible mode of operation is idle mode, where the MS remains stored for later use and does not circulate through the system. The operating strategy of the investigated system will be determined by a dispatch optimization algorithm that will be introduced in the following sections.

3. Balancing Services Market

Since the proposed P2H system coupled with TES provides sufficient dynamic response and operational flexibility, this study considers not only electricity procurement on the day-ahead market (DAM) but also trading of technical flexibility, i.e., participation in the balancing services market. For demand-side assets such as TES system with an electric heater, the most suitable service is the provision of negative automatic frequency restoration reserve (AFRR-).

3.1. aFRR Market Mechanism

Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve is a balancing service that helps maintain grid frequency stability. It is automatically activated by the transmission system operator (TSO) in response to frequency deviations. Balancing service providers (BSPs) offering aFRR must ensure that their contracted reserve is fully activated within five minutes. Due to its nature, aFRR is characterized by frequent activations throughout the day. Positive aFRR (aFRR+) corresponds to an upward regulation in which the BSP increases active power injection into the grid. Conversely, negative aFRR (aFRR-) represents a downward regulation, where the BSP reduces generation or increases consumption, thereby absorbing power from the grid.

- Capacity Reservation: Capacity for aFRR is procured through daily auctions organized either at the national level or via shared international platforms such as ALPACA. The allocation follows a pay-as-bid principle. Offers are ranked according to the bid price, and the

required capacity is selected by an optimization algorithm, with successful bidders receiving their individual bid price. The minimum bid size for participation is 1 MW, with a bidding granularity of 1 MW.

- **Balancing Energy Activation:** The activation of regulation energy (RE) is coordinated through the international PICASSO platform, which integrates aFRR providers across Europe. The PICASSO algorithm runs at a 4-second resolution, continuously optimizing and dispatching the most cost-efficient resources to restore system balance. Here, a marginal pricing mechanism applies. For aFRR+, a BSP is activated if its bid price is lower than the marginal price. For aFRR-, the same principle applies but with reversed logic due to the sign convention: the BSP is activated if its bid price is higher than the marginal price.

3.2. Revenue structure

The remuneration structure for aFRR consists of two complementary revenue streams:

- Capacity Revenue (availability payment) – BSPs receive payment for holding reserve capacity available for activation, regardless of whether activation occurs. Capacity remuneration is typically expressed in EUR/MW.h. In the studied system, where the P2H element is an EH, the contracted aFRR- reserve is limited by the EH's installed power.
- Energy Revenue (activation payment) – BSPs are also compensated for the actual regulation energy (RE) delivered during reserve activations. This element of remuneration reflects the real-time provision of flexibility to the system. Energy payment is expressed in EUR/MWh.

It should be noted that when the BSP is activated to provide aFRR- service, energy-dependent network charges apply. Consequently, in this study, all references to energy revenue from the aFRR-market refer to net revenue, defined as the activation payment from TSO the BSP minus the applicable energy-dependent network charges.

3.3. Bid price determination

The BSP submits two distinct bid prices: (i) the bid price for capacity reservation and (ii) the bid price for activation of RE. In this paper, the bid price for capacity reservation in a given hour is conservatively calculated as the average price on the capacity reservation market during that hour.

From an economic perspective, activation of RE is attractive whenever the marginal price in the balancing market falls below the provider's opportunity cost of heat production. The relevant alternative in this case is generating the same amount of heat using electricity purchased on the DAM; thus the benefit equals the avoided electricity expenditure on the DAM. In other words, it is economically rational to submit a bid for activation at a level lower than the effective cost of producing the heat through electricity procured on the DAM. An approach based on this principle

Table 2
MILP model variables

Parameter/Set	Unit	Description
Sets		
τ	[-]	Set of time periods t in the time horizon
Time-indexed parameters		
$Q_{th}(t)$	[MW _{th}]	Thermal load
$p_{DAM}(t)$	[€/MWh]	Electricity DAM price
$p_{RE}(t)$	[€/MWh]	Average marginal RE activation price
$p_{cap}(t)$	[€/MW.h]	Capacity reservation price
$BidSR(t)$	[MW _{th}]	Success rate of the bidding process
$RE_{time}(t)$	[%]	Percentage of hour RE is activated
Sizing parameters		
P_{EHnom}	[MW _e]	Nominal EH electric power
E_{TESnom}	[MWh _{th}]	Nominal TES thermal capacity
Parameters and constraints		
η_{EH}	[%]	EH efficiency
η_{SGS}	[%]	Steam generation system efficiency
P_{EHmin}	[%]	Min. EH power as a percentage of P_{EHnom}
P_{EHmax}	[%]	Max. EH power as a percentage of P_{EHnom}
SoC_{min}	[%]	Min. TES State of charge
SoC_{max}	[%]	Max. TES State of charge
RE_{act}	[%]	Percentage of reserved capacity activated
p_{dist}	[€/MWh]	Sum of energy-related regulated network fees
Continuous variables		
$SoC(t)$	[%]	TES State of Charge
$P_{EH}^{DAM}(t)$	[MW _e]	EH power supplied by DAM electricity
$P_{EH}^{aFRR}(t)$	[MW _e]	EH power supplied by activation of RE
$Cap_{aFRR}(t)$	[MW _e]	Provided reserved capacity
$P_{loss}(t)$	[MW _{th}]	Heat losses from TES system
Binary variables		
$X(t)$	[-]	1 if EH is running at time t ; otherwise 0

is used to determine the bid price for activating RE in this paper.

Note that positive values of RE price indicate payments from the BSP to the TSO, whereas negative values correspond to payments from the TSO to the BSP. The RE is activated only when the balancing market marginal price falls below the bid price. For example, setting the bid price to 10 EUR/MWh means that the BSP is willing to pay up to 10 EUR/MWh upon activation (marginal price lower than 10 EUR/MWh). Conversely, setting the bid price to -10 EUR/MWh indicates that the BSP wants to be activated only

if the TSO pays at least 10 EUR/MWh (marginal price lower than -10 EUR/MWh).

4. Methods

The methodology adopted in this study is presented in this section. First, the dispatch optimization algorithm, formulated as a mixed-integer linear program (MILP), is developed. Next, a detailed heat transfer assessment is performed to quantify thermal losses, which are then used as inputs for the dispatch optimization model. Subsequently, a bottom-up economic model is presented to evaluate the economic performance of the proposed system. Several techno-economic KPIs are defined to assess the system and benchmark it

against conventional technologies. Based on one of these KPIs, the Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH), an optimal system sizing is determined. Finally, the methodology used for CO₂ emissions evaluation is outlined.

The dispatch optimization MILP algorithm is implemented in General Algebraic Modelling System (GAMS) tool and solved with the Cplex 22.1.0.0 solver, with integrality gap of 0.01. The model runs with a one-hour time step over a one-year optimization horizon. The thermal loss model and the economic model were implemented in Python, and all subsequent post-processing calculations were also performed in Python.

$$F = \min \left[\sum_{t=0}^N (p_{\text{DAM}} + p_{\text{dist}}) P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{DAM}} + (p_{\text{RE}} + p_{\text{dist}}) P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{aFRR}} - Cap_{\text{aFRR}} p_{\text{cap}} \right] \forall t \in \tau \quad (1)$$

$$SoC(t) = SoC(t-1) + \frac{[P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{DAM}}(t) + P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{aFRR}}(t)] \cdot \eta_{\text{EH}} - \frac{Q_{\text{th}}(t)}{\eta_{\text{SGS}}} - P_{\text{loss}}(t-1)}{E_{\text{TESnom}}} \forall t > 0 \quad (2)$$

$$P_{\text{loss}}(t-1) = c_0 + c_1 \cdot SoC(t-1) \forall t \in \tau \quad (3)$$

$$X(t) \cdot P_{\text{EH,min}} \leq \frac{P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{DAM}}(t) + P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{aFRR}}(t)}{P_{\text{EHnom}}} \leq X(t) \cdot P_{\text{EH,max}} \forall t \in \tau \quad (4)$$

$$SoC_{\text{min}} \leq SoC(t) \leq SoC_{\text{max}} \forall t \in \tau \quad (5)$$

$$Cap_{\text{aFRR}}(t) \leq (P_{\text{EHnom}} \cdot P_{\text{EH,max}} - P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{DAM}}(t)) \cdot BidSR(t) \forall t \in \tau \quad (6)$$

$$Cap_{\text{aFRR}}(t) \cdot \eta_{\text{EH}} \leq SoC_{\text{max}} \cdot E_{\text{TESnom}} - SoC(t-1) \forall t > 0 \quad (7)$$

$$P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{aFRR}}(t) = Cap_{\text{aFRR}}(t) \cdot RE_{\text{time}}(t) \cdot BidSR(t) \cdot RE_{\text{act}} \forall t \in \tau \quad (8)$$

4.1. Dispatch optimization model

The goal of the studied system is to supply process steam to the industrial customer on demand. Without TES, the P2H system would consume electricity exactly at the same time as heat is demanded. TES integration allows for demand-side management by shifting electricity consumption to low-price periods and storing thermal energy to meet later heat demand. The charging schedule is therefore guided by market conditions, but remains constrained by the heat demand and the technical limits of the TES-integrated P2H system. In addition to participation in the DAM, the system is also studied in the context of flexible electricity markets, where it can provide balancing services to the grid. As a result, the dispatch schedule is further influenced by the requirements and opportunities of these balancing markets.

In this paper, operating schedule is determined by developing an optimization model formulated as MILP. MILP is a widely used method for handling optimization problems

that involve both continuous and discrete variables, allowing precise scheduling decisions while respecting system constraints. MILP provides an effective way to achieve optimal operation in complex, dynamic systems such as the studied P2H+TES system, operating on both the DAM and aFRR-market.

The developed model integrates variable DAM electricity prices together with both reserve provision commitments and activation signals from the aFRR- balancing market, while also accounting for thermal demand profile as well as the system's technical and operational constraints. The parameters and variables employed in the MILP-based dispatch optimization are summarized in Table 2.

4.1.1. Objective function

The objective of the dispatch optimization algorithm is to minimize variable OPEX and maximize aFRR revenues. This is represented in Eq. (1).

Variable OPEX is limited to the cost of electricity consumed by the EH. Auxiliary equipment electricity consumption (e.g., MS pumps, water pumps, monitoring system) is insignificant compared to the EH load. Therefore, it is omitted from the objective function but accounted for in the overall economic model. Furthermore, only variable regulated electricity network charges are considered in the optimization process. Parameter p_{dist} is the sum of all energy-dependent regulated network charges. Fixed capacity network charges do not affect the optimization; therefore, they are excluded from the objective function but included in the overall economic model. The values of all regulated electricity network charges are described in A.2.

4.1.2. System constraints

The State of Charge (SoC) of the TES system is defined by the energy balance in Eq. (2). Assuming the tanks are maintained at their nominal temperature level, the heat losses, $P_{\text{loss}}(t)$, depend on the $SOC(t)$ of the TES system, which is in reality given by the level of MS in the tanks. A simplifying assumption is made where the thermal losses are modeled as a linear function of $SOC(t-1)$, as shown in Eq. (3). This results in a one-hour delay in calculating thermal losses, which is acceptable due to the high thermal inertia of the TES system and is assumed to have minimal impact on overall accuracy. The estimation of heat losses, including the coefficients c_0 and c_1 of the linear function, is detailed in section 4.2.

Constraints defined by Eq.(4) and Eq. (5) ensure that EH power and TES SoC stay within their operational ranges.

4.1.3. aFRR market constraints

The following formulas represent constraints for balancing services provided by the investigated system. These formulas also define the technical connection between reserved capacity and RE activated from that capacity. Equation (6) describes the available reserve, that is limited to the unused portion of the EH's maximum power. The bid aFRR capacity is constrained not only by available EH power, but also by the remaining TES capacity, represented by the SoC. Actual amount of regulation energy delivered, and thus the resulting aFRR market revenues, is calculated using historical data, which determine the fraction of each hour, during which the BSP is activated (based on the bid price). Nevertheless, Eq. (7) enforces a worst-case activation constraint by limiting the bid aFRR capacity to a level that can be sustained over the entire bidding time window, in accordance with TSO requirements. This approach prevents overestimating aFRR market revenues for storage technologies and is consistent with standard practice in techno-economic sizing studies.

The relationship between balancing reserves and the corresponding RE depends on three quantities, namely $BidSR(t)$, RE_{act} and $RE_{\text{time}}(t)$. The $BidSR(t)$ is a binary parameter that indicates the probabilistic success rate (SR) of securing reserved capacity in the bidding process. For instance, if the annual success rate is 90 %, the time series for the year would reflect this as 1 for 90 % of the time steps

Figure 2: RE_{act} value for provided reserved capacity at aFRR market.

Figure 3: Example of determining $RE_{\text{time}}(t)$ and $p_{\text{RE}}(t)$ from 4 second averaged prices of activated RE on the Picasso platform.

and 0 for the remaining 10 %. Next, the RE_{act} describes the average activated aFRR energy from the reserved capacity in the selected hour. A decreasing trend with increasing provided reserve capacity is assumed, as illustrated in Fig. 2. This reflects a conservative assumption that, as more reserved capacity is offered, a smaller share of it will be activated for balancing energy. Finally, the $RE_{\text{time}}(t)$ denotes the fraction of time within an hour during which the RE is activated. The determination of $RE_{\text{time}}(t)$, based on the bid price, is explained in section 4.1.4.

4.1.4. Determination of aFRR market parameters

Figure 3 demonstrates how parameters $RE_{\text{time}}(t)$ and $p_{\text{RE}}(t)$ are determined in the selected hour. Parameter $p_{\text{RE}}(t)$ represents the average marginal price at which the RE is activated in the selected hour based on the bid price for that hour. The determination of bid price for activation of RE was explained in 3.3. The amount of activated RE is defined by eq. (8). Figure 3 presents 4-second averaged prices of activated RE from aFRR- reserves, indicating the periods when the BSPs with bid prices of 10 EUR/MWh and -20 EUR/MWh were activated. For each period, the aFRR-regulating energy price is shown.

As can be seen, the higher the bid price, the more frequent the activation, leading to increased heat production by the electric heater in the proposed system. For the bid price of 10 EUR/MWh, the average marginal price p_{RE} within the

Figure 4: TES tank's heat loss schematics

hour is -37 EUR/MWh and the provider would be activated for 85 % of the hour, as indicated by RE_{time} . For the bid price of -20 EUR/MWh, the p_{RE} is -126 EUR/MWh during the selected hour, indicating a higher payment from the TSO to the BSP due to the sign convention, but activation would occur for only 22 % of the hour.

4.1.5. Model limitations

As a modelling simplification, market trading rules, specifically gate closure time, are not incorporated. This assumption reflects the deterministic nature of the input data, thereby limiting the full representation of the temporal dynamics of market operations and uncertainty in prices or activations. Inputs such as DAM and RE prices, activation volumes, and reserve clearing are treated as deterministic or expected values. As a result, the model cannot quantify risk (e.g., the impact of low activation or adverse prices).

This idealization is only partially mitigated by using average bid prices for balancing reserves and by imposing a 90 % annual success rate in reserve auctions through $BidSR(t)$ coefficient. Furthermore, the model operates with an hourly time resolution, whereas in reality market participants can update bid prices at quarter-hourly intervals. Next, competition among providers and market clearing are not modelled. The capacities and bids of other participants are exogenous. Strategic interactions, market power, or the price impact of one's own bid are not captured. The BSP's behaviour is likewise simplified.

4.2. Thermal loss model

A one-dimensional steady-state heat transfer analysis is used to estimate thermal losses from the MS storage tanks in the presented techno-economic model. A vertical-cylindrical tank with one layer of insulation is considered, as depicted in Fig. 4. The model also considers two height reserves: h_{MS} represents the portion of tank that must always be filled with molten salt to ensure MS pump operation and h_{air} is the buffer height between the maximum salt level and the tank roof. It is assumed that the tank is mounted on a supporting frame, i.e. it is surrounded by ambient air on all sides. The following simplifications were considered in the heat transfer analysis: (i) the tank is modeled as a cylinder (disregarding the spherical shape of the bottom and roof), i.e. cylindrical conduction model is chosen for tank wall and planar conduction model for the roof and bottom, (ii) heat transfer by radiation is neglected, (iii) both fluids inside the tank have a uniform temperature distribution and same temperature, thus internal heat transfer between the fluids is neglected. The tank's inner volume is divided into two sections: a wet region (where MS is in contact with the wall) and a dry region (empty top part, where gas is in contact with the wall). The height of these sections (level of MS) changes with varying SoC of the TES system. Specific heat transfer coefficients are calculated for each section. This represents a widely used approach to account for the varying MS level in a storage tank [32], [35], [36].

$$P_{\text{loss, HOT}}(SoC) = Q_{\text{wet, HOT}}(SoC) + Q_{\text{dry, HOT}}(SoC) + Q_{\text{b, HOT}} + Q_{\text{r, HOT}} \quad (9)$$

$$P_{\text{loss, HOT}}(SoC) = \left(\frac{1}{R_{\text{wet, HOT}}(SoC)} + \frac{1}{R_{\text{dry, HOT}}(SoC)} + \frac{1}{R_{\text{b, HOT}}} + \frac{1}{R_{\text{r, HOT}}} \right) (T_{\text{HOT}} - T_{\text{amb}}) \quad (10)$$

$$R_{\text{wet, hot}}(SoC) = \frac{1}{h_{\text{wet, hot}} A_{\text{wet, i, hot}}(SoC)} + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{r_i + d_{\text{wall}}}{r_i}\right)}{2\pi L_{\text{wet}}(SoC) k_{\text{wall}}} + \frac{\ln\left(\frac{r_i + d_{\text{wall}} + d_{\text{ins}}}{r_i + d_{\text{wall}}}\right)}{2\pi L_{\text{wet}}(SoC) k_{\text{ins}}} + \frac{1}{h_{\text{amb}} A_{\text{wet, o, hot}}(SoC)} \quad (11)$$

$$R_{\text{b, hot}} = \frac{1}{h_{\text{b, hot}} A_{\text{b, hot}}} + \frac{d_{\text{wall}}}{A_{\text{b, hot}} k_{\text{wall}}} + \frac{d_{\text{ins}}}{A_{\text{b, hot}} k_{\text{ins}}} + \frac{1}{h_{\text{amb}} A_{\text{b, hot}}} \quad (12)$$

$$P_{\text{loss}}(SoC) = SF (P_{\text{loss, HOT}}(SoC) + P_{\text{loss, COLD}}(SoC)) \quad (13)$$

The total hot tank heat losses are given by the sum of heat losses through the wet wall (Q_{wet}), the dry wall (Q_{dry}), tank's bottom (Q_{b}) and tank's roof (Q_{r}), as stated in (9). This can be expressed using Eq. (10), where the respective thermal resistances are considered. The individual thermal resistances consider natural convective heat transfer inside and outside the tank as well as heat conduction through the vessel's wall and insulation. Eq. (11) is formulated for the wet wall but is equally applicable to the dry wall. Likewise, Eq. (12) describes the thermal resistance at the tank bottom and can also be used for the roof.

In the equations above, h refers to the heat transfer coefficient, T is temperature, A is the surface area, r denotes perimeter and $L_{\text{wet/dry}}$ is the wetted/dry height of the tank (corresponding to the SoC), d denotes thickness, and k is the thermal conductivity coefficient. Subscripts 'wall', 'ins', 'i', 'o', 'amb' refer to wall, insulation, inner area, outer area and ambient, respectively.

$$Nu = 0.13 (Gr Pr)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (14)$$

$$Nu = 0.27 (Gr Pr)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (15)$$

The convective heat transfer between fluid inside the tank and its inner wall is approximated by a correlation for vertical cylinder using Eq.(14), while the heat transfer at the tank's bottom and roof is estimated using a correlation for a horizontal plate using Eq. (15) [37].

Total heat losses, considering SoC-dependent losses from both cold and hot tank, are calculated using Eq.(13), where SF represents a safety factor, which is set to 1.5 as a conservative assumption. The calculation was performed for TES SoC values ranging from 0 % to 100 % (varying MS level in the hot and cold tanks). Through linear approximation of the calculated data, the coefficients of the linear function described in Eq. (3) are obtained. The parameters used in the heat loss analysis are listed in section A.1.

4.3. Economic model

To analyze the economic viability of different scenarios and allow for their comparison, several economic key performance indicators (KPIs) are defined, including capital expenditure (CAPEX), operational expenses (OPEX), balancing market revenue (REV), net operational costs (NOC), net operational benefit (NOB), and the Net Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH).

The CAPEX input data are described in table 3. CAPEX include the cost of heat storage medium (molten salts), storage system (tanks, insulation, supporting structure), charging system (EH), SGS (heat exchangers), grid integration (transformer, metering), energy management system costs and Balance of System (BoS) consisting of valves, pumps and piping. Indirect CAPEX is also considered, covering EPC fee (engineering, installation, commissioning) and project development costs (project management, financing, licensing).

Table 3
CAPEX and Decommissioning input data

Component	Value	Unit
Molten salts	1.1	€/kg [38]
Storage system	14.8	€/kWh _{th} [38]
Balance of System	25	€/kWh _{th} [32]
Steam generation system	120	€/kWh _{th} [32]
Charging system	114	€/kW _e [39]
Grid integration	12	€/kW _e [39]
Energy management system	100 000	€ [32]
EPC & Project development	30	% of direct CAPEX [39]
Decommissioning costs	5	% of direct CAPEX [38]

1 EUR ≈ 1 USD is assumed.

OPEX constitute mostly of electricity-related costs, specifically the market and the regulated component. The market electricity costs are determined by the dispatch optimization algorithm. The structure and values of regulated network charges are provided in the Annex, Table 8. Additional 1 % of these electricity-related costs is added to account for auxiliary equipment electricity consumption, such as MS pumps, water pumps, and monitoring systems. Furthermore, annual operation and maintenance (O&M) costs and annual replacement costs are considered, corresponding to 2 % and 1 % of the direct CAPEX, respectively.

For scenarios, where the system provides aFRR- services, revenues from the balancing market are generated. The value of REV is estimated by the developed MILP dispatch optimization algorithm. The structure of revenues, as described in Section 3.2, consists of two components: capacity revenue and energy revenue. Net energy revenue refers to the revenue obtained from providing RE after deducting the costs associated with energy-dependent network fees.

Next, the net operational cost is defined as OPEX minus the REV obtained from ancillary service provision. Negative NOC values indicate that REV exceed OPEX, resulting in positive operational balance. This convention aligns with the cost-minimization framing used in the dispatch optimization algorithm.

Another KPI, referred to as the Net Operational Benefit (NOB), is introduced to compare the performance of the proposed system (scenario A) with alternative technology (scenario B), e.g., an electric boiler, as defined in (16).

$$NOB_A = OPEX_B - OPEX_A + REV_A \quad (16)$$

$$LCOH = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{(CAPEX_n + OPEX_n - REV_n + DEC_n)}{(1+r_d)^n}}{\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{Q_n}{(1+r_d)^n}} \quad (17)$$

Table 4

Studied sizing configurations of the system

EH power [MW]	TES capacity [MWh]			
	10	20	40	80
5	x	x	x	
10	x	x	x	x
20		x	x	x

Finally, to assess the cost-effectiveness of the proposed heat generation system over its lifetime, net levelized cost of heat is calculated. This metrics determines the average cost of supplied unit of heat while considering all associated expenses over the system's entire lifetime, such as CAPEX, OPEX or decommissioning costs. In case of providing ancillary services, the proposed system can also generate revenue which is subtracted from the expenses in the LCOH formula given in (17). If these revenues exceed the total lifetime costs, the resulting net LCOH may become negative, indicating that the system yields a net economic profit. In such cases, negative LCOH values should be interpreted as a sign of economic benefit rather than implying that heat is produced at a negative price.

The net LCOH is estimated using annual values, assuming that all OPEX, REV and heat demand follow the same yearly profile throughout the system's lifetime N . CAPEX is assumed to occur in year 0, while decommissioning is scheduled in year $N+1$. A 30-year operational period is considered in line with [38]. A discount rate r_d of 7 % is applied.

4.4. Sizing optimization

The optimal sizing configuration is determined based on the minimum LCOH value. The sizing parameters of the proposed system include the EH nominal power and the TES capacity, which are independent of each other. Several sizing configurations are evaluated assuming a modular system architecture. To limit the number of scenarios, only selected configurations were analyzed; these studied cases are highlighted in Table 4.

4.5. CO₂ emissions assessment

Another key factor in comparing industrial heat generation systems is their associated greenhouse gas emissions. To evaluate this, hourly grid carbon intensity data for the analyzed markets are used to capture temporal variations in electricity-related emissions. Annual CO₂ savings are then calculated as the difference between annual CO₂ emissions of a benchmark scenario and those of the proposed P2H+TES system. The input data are described in 5.3.4.

5. Case study

A comprehensive description of the input datasets employed for the analysis is provided in this section. The developed methodology is employed to assess the performance of the proposed system through a case study of a real plastic manufacturing plant in the Czech Republic. The industrial

Table 5

Parameters of the system (base case scenario)

Parameter	Value	Unit
TES capacity	10	MWh _{th}
MS mass	85	t
Tank dimensions (diameter; height)	3 ; 6.5	m ; m
Hot tank operational temperature	480	°C
Cold tank operational temperature	180	°C
EH nominal power	5	MW _e
EH (charging) efficiency	95	%
EH operational range	10 - 100	% *
Steam delivery temperature	220	°C
Maximum thermal load	3	MW _{th}
SGS (discharging) efficiency	97	%
TES SoC operational range	0 - 100	%

* % of nominal power

Figure 5: Heat loss for varying SoC (base case scenario).

facility produces plastic compounds and requires saturated steam at 220°C (2.3 MPa), with condensate returned at 80°C and atmospheric pressure.

5.1. Case study parameters

The key technical and sizing parameters for the base case scenario are presented in Table 5. The base case scenario considers EH nominal power of 5 MW_e and TES capacity of 10 MWh_{th}. The YARA MOST inventory already accounts for the minimum level necessary for proper molten salt pump operation, resulting in a TES system SoC range from 0 % to 100 %.

5.2. Thermal loss estimation

The results of the thermal loss estimation are presented here for the base case scenario. The heat loss values corresponding to varying SoC (MS level in the tanks) are shown in Fig. 5. The points represent the calculated data, while the dashed lines show the linear fits. It is evident that the heat loss value does not change significantly with varying SoC. However, from the perspective of the optimization algorithm, the authors considered it important to include the dependency described by (3) to allow the system in stand-by

mode to distinguish between a full hot tank and a full cold tank, potentially leading to a preference for cold stand-by regime for longer idle periods.

Under the modularity assumption, an increase in system capacity directly corresponds to an increase in the number of tanks. Consequently, for scenarios with scaled capacities, thermal losses rise proportionally.

5.3. Model input datasets

The datasets serving as inputs to the MILP dispatch optimization algorithm within this case study are detailed in the following subsections.

5.3.1. Thermal load

The thermal load profile employed in this study was derived from information on the typical operating characteristics of the selected plastic compound manufacturing facility. While the hourly load data are confidential, the available information indicates that the thermal demand is generally constant, with only minor interruptions due to short-term outages or scheduled maintenance. Based on this characterization, a representative profile was constructed, assuming a constant thermal demand of 3 MW_{th} , with two planned two-week shutdowns distributed over the year. The thermal load data are pre-processed before being introduced into the MILP optimization algorithm to incorporate additional thermal load, namely the transient thermal demand associated with system warm-up after shutdowns. The warm-up period is assumed to last 20 minutes, thus additional load equal to one third of the subsequent hourly demand is applied. It is also assumed, that the thermal load already accounts for preheating of the feedwater to 150°C to avoid the risk of freezing of the MS in the economizer.

5.3.2. Electricity DAM prices

The performance of the proposed P2H+TES system is investigated within two market zones, the Czech (CZ) and the German-Luxembourg (DE) day-ahead electricity markets, to assess the impacts of market characteristics on the economic feasibility. This study uses electricity DAM prices from 2024, gathered from [40] for CZ and [41] for DE zone. The electricity prices throughout year 2024 are depicted in Fig. 6. Despite the interconnection of the transmission grids, price differences between the CZ and DE markets arise during certain hours due to limited cross-border transmission capacity, particularly during periods of high renewable energy generation in Germany.

Main statistical information about CZ and DE markets are included in Fig. 6. In 2024, the CZ market exhibited a higher average electricity price, while the DE market was characterized by greater price volatility and a significantly higher number of hours with zero or negative prices. As the share of intermittent renewable energy sources in the energy mix continues to grow, the CZ DAM market is expected to increasingly reflect the price dynamics observed in the DE market, making the DE market a useful reference for the future development of the CZ market.

Figure 6: Day-ahead electricity market prices in 2024 for CZ and DE zone.

5.3.3. aFRR market prices

The calculations in this work are based on data from the year 2024, covering both the CZ and DE balancing markets. Capacity revenues are estimated using the reserve capacity price data. For the Czech market, the prices represent average accepted bid prices for the respective hours in the national market, collected from [42]. For the German market, the data correspond to average accepted bid prices aggregated over four-hour blocks as published on the ALPACA platform [43].

Fig. 9 illustrates the variation in aFRR- capacity prices for a selected day in May 2024. Whereas CZ aFRR- prices are relatively stable throughout the day, DE aFRR- prices exhibit significant intraday variability. In 2024, the average aFRR- capacity price in the Czech Republic amounted to 10.1 EUR/MW.h with a standard deviation of 18.4 EUR/MW.h. In Germany, the corresponding annual average was 14.5 EUR/MW.h with a standard deviation of 20.6 EUR/MW.h.

Energy revenues are evaluated based on 4-second averaged prices of activated balancing energy obtained from the Picasso platform [42]. For balancing energy, marginal prices can vary between +15 000 and -15 000 EUR/MWh. Although both the CZ and DE participate in the PICASSO platform, the resulting prices are not always fully harmonized. This divergence is primarily attributable to cross-border transmission capacity limitations.

Figures 7 and 8 present heat maps of marginal RE prices on the PICASSO platform for 2024, covering the Czech bidding zone and the German control area of 50Hertz. The heat maps indicate that aFRR- prices are predominantly concentrated (approximately two-thirds of the time) within the range of 25–100 EUR/MWh, corresponding to more frequent settlements in which the BSP compensates the TSO. The annual average prices of 20.66 EUR/MWh in the Czech market and 39.75 EUR/MWh in the German market also reflect an overall trend of payments from the BSP to the TSO.

5.3.4. Grid emission factor

Hourly grid carbon intensity data for the year 2024 were obtained from [44, 45] for the CZ grid and from [46] for DE grid. The reported electricity emission factor reflects

Service	aFRR-	Price intervals [EUR/MWh]																									
		Payment from BSP to the TSO										Payment from the TSO to the BSP															
Year	Month	>=300	(250, 300]	(200, 250]	(150, 200]	(125, 150]	(100, 125]	(75, 100]	(50, 75]	(25, 50]	(0, 25]	(-50, 0]	(-100, -50]	(-200, -100]	(-300, -200]	(-1000, -300]	(-2000, -1000]	(-3000, -2000]	(-4000, -3000]	(-5000, -4000]	(-6000, -5000]	(-7000, -6000]	(-8000, -7000]	(-9000, -8000]	(-10000, -9000]	>-10000	
2024	January	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.2%	35.8%	23.0%	8.9%	13.0%	11.8%	1.5%	1.5%	0.1%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	
	February	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%	17.6%	36.3%	16.8%	15.8%	10.6%	0.9%	1.3%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	
	March	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%	7.7%	41.1%	17.5%	12.9%	13.7%	2.1%	3.7%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	
	April	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.7%	15.6%	31.4%	9.3%	12.9%	19.3%	5.2%	4.7%	0.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%
	May	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.8%	2.5%	35.1%	18.6%	11.2%	20.1%	3.5%	5.5%	0.8%	0.8%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.1%	
	June	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%	1.4%	4.0%	32.3%	26.6%	11.5%	16.1%	3.1%	2.9%	0.3%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%	
	July	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.8%	4.2%	41.9%	22.7%	10.6%	12.0%	2.3%	4.2%	0.3%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	
	August	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	1.3%	3.6%	27.2%	19.6%	13.2%	9.5%	15.5%	2.6%	5.2%	0.8%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	
	September	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.9%	2.2%	15.0%	29.7%	14.4%	13.5%	15.3%	4.3%	4.0%	0.2%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	
	October	0.5%	0.5%	0.2%	0.2%	1.2%	1.9%	18.7%	30.4%	20.0%	9.1%	13.7%	1.8%	1.5%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	
	November	1.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.9%	2.6%	33.3%	28.4%	16.0%	9.1%	7.5%	0.3%	0.3%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	
	December	0.1%	0.3%	0.1%	0.1%	1.0%	4.1%	29.2%	21.8%	17.7%	11.1%	13.0%	0.7%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	

Figure 7: CZ aFRR- RE prices distribution

Service	aFRR-	Price intervals [EUR/MWh]																								
		Payment from BSP to the TSO										Payment from the TSO to the BSP														
Year	Month	>=300	(250, 300]	(200, 250]	(150, 200]	(125, 150]	(100, 125]	(75, 100]	(50, 75]	(25, 50]	(0, 25]	(-50, 0]	(-100, -50]	(-200, -100]	(-300, -200]	(-1000, -300]	(-2000, -1000]	(-3000, -2000]	(-4000, -3000]	(-5000, -4000]	(-6000, -5000]	(-7000, -6000]	(-8000, -7000]	(-9000, -8000]	(-10000, -9000]	>-10000
2024	January	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	4.4%	30.9%	24.8%	11.4%	11.5%	11.3%	3.2%	2.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	February	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	12.0%	34.7%	21.9%	15.5%	10.1%	2.8%	2.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	March	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.3%	1.2%	9.5%	33.3%	24.5%	10.6%	7.4%	4.2%	7.8%	0.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	April	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	1.4%	12.0%	28.2%	13.1%	9.8%	15.4%	8.2%	10.0%	1.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	May	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.6%	1.8%	6.7%	29.4%	16.2%	9.5%	18.5%	6.8%	7.6%	1.6%	0.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	June	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	1.0%	2.7%	6.3%	29.8%	22.5%	11.5%	15.0%	3.4%	6.0%	1.2%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	July	0.2%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%	0.9%	2.0%	7.2%	31.4%	23.3%	11.0%	11.0%	4.0%	8.0%	0.4%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	August	0.6%	0.0%	0.1%	0.4%	1.9%	3.6%	22.3%	19.5%	15.5%	9.6%	10.8%	4.6%	9.1%	2.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	September	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	1.2%	1.9%	4.9%	17.9%	22.5%	16.1%	10.3%	9.9%	5.9%	8.6%	0.5%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	October	0.6%	0.6%	0.2%	0.4%	1.5%	3.2%	22.2%	27.0%	19.0%	7.5%	10.1%	2.9%	4.6%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	November	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.8%	2.7%	35.9%	28.1%	17.1%	5.6%	4.9%	1.6%	1.7%	0.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	December	0.2%	0.4%	0.2%	0.4%	1.4%	5.3%	29.1%	20.2%	17.4%	9.3%	9.2%	2.4%	4.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Figure 8: DE aFRR- RE prices distribution

Figure 9: Comparison of balancing reserve prices on CZ and DE aFRR- market for chosen day in 2024.

domestic power generation only and does not account for cross-border electricity imports or exports.

The distribution of grid emission factors is shown in Fig. 10. The figure indicates that the average annual grid emission factor in DE grid is lower than in CZ grid. It also shows that the emission factors in the DE zone are more evenly distributed across the full minimum–maximum range, whereas the CZ emission factors are concentrated predominantly at values higher than 0.4 tCO₂e/MWh.

Figure 10: Distribution of grid emission factors in 2024 in CZ and DE zone.

5.4. Scenarios description

Several scenarios are defined to evaluate system performance under varying operational and market conditions. These include operation solely in the DAM (DAM scenario) and combined participation in the DAM and ancillary

Table 6
Techno-economic KPIs for DAM and DAM+AS scenarios (CZ)

Parameter	DAM	DAM+AS	Unit
TES capacity		10	MWh _{th}
EH nominal power		5	MW _e
Thermal load		24.34	GWh _{th} /y
Electricity consumption		26.73	GWh _e /y
Electricity from DAM	100	66	%
Electricity from aFRR-	0	34	%
TES thermal loss	0.31	0.31	GWh _{th} /y
RTE	91	91	%
Total CAPEX		2.37	M€
Total OPEX	2.99	2.05	M€/y
Capacity Revenue	0	0.23	M€/y
Net Energy Revenue	0	0.16	M€/y
Net operational costs	2.99	1.65	M€/y
LCOH	131.04	75.79	€/MWh

services market (DAM+AS scenario). These scenarios are further analyzed under varying conditions, including different electricity market zones (CZ and DE). The considered base-case sizing is 5 MW_e of EH power and 10 MWh_{th} of TES capacity. Alternative system sizing configurations are studied to identify the most cost-optimal design.

The results of the techno-economic performance of the proposed system are benchmarked against conventional industrial heat generation technology, an electric boiler (EB scenario) without buffer storage. The EB is assumed to procure electricity on DAM and have an installed capacity of 5 MW_e in all scenarios (designed to meet the heat demand) with an efficiency of 98 % [47].

6. Results

For each scenario (DAM and DAM+AS), the optimal system operation over a representative time window is illustrated based on the dispatch optimization results. Subsequently, the key techno-economic performance indicators (KPIs) are reported, including a comparison between the Czech and German market outcomes. Finally, the proposed P2H+TES system is benchmarked against a conventional electric boiler scenario.

6.1. DAM scenario

Figure 11 illustrates the operation of the proposed system on the DAM, as determined by the MILP-based dispatch optimization algorithm, for three representative days. It is evident that the demand-side flexibility of the TES-integrated P2H system is effectively utilized, as the operation takes advantage of the full SoC range of the TES system. Two daily price spikes are observed in the analyzed period, during which charging is avoided. The EH power profile corresponds to low-price periods, indicating cost-optimal dispatch behavior. Within the selected time horizon, the highest DAM price reached 120 €/MWh, whereas the

Figure 11: Operation for chosen 3 days in May 2024. (DAM Scenario, CZ, base case sizing)

Figure 12: CAPEX and annual OPEX structure (DAM Scenario, CZ, base case sizing).

maximum price at which the system operated in charging mode was 105 €/MWh.

The techno-economic performance parameters for base case sizing scenario are summarized in Table 6. The total power-to-heat round-trip efficiency (RTE), accounting for conversion losses in the P2H system and SGS as well as thermal losses from the TES tanks, is 91 %.

Figure 12 presents the breakdown of both CAPEX and annual OPEX components. SGS, charging system, and indirect costs constitute the largest shares of CAPEX, while electricity-related costs dominate the total OPEX, with wholesale electricity costs accounting for 63 %. Regulated network charges also contribute significantly to the overall OPEX.

Figure 13: Energy-dependent OPEX (DAM costs + energy-dependent regulated network charges) for different sizing configurations.

Figure 14: Total OPEX for different sizing configurations.

Next, OPEX of different sizing configurations were analyzed. Greater EH installed power allows faster charging during periods of low electricity market prices. Similarly, higher TES capacity enables the system to bypass periods of high electricity market prices. If only the energy-dependent electricity-related OPEX are assumed, their value decreases with increase in EH power, as shown in Fig. 13. A similar decreasing trend is observed for increasing TES capacities. However, this reduction continues only up to a certain point, since larger TES capacities are also associated with higher thermal losses (given the modular design assumption adopted in this study). As demonstrated in the 5 MW_e case, increasing TES capacity from 10 MWh_{th} to 20 MWh_{th} significantly reduces OPEX, but a further increase to 40 MWh_{th} causes OPEX to slightly rise again. At 20 MWh_{th}, the system has already exploited most of its flexibility potential, and any additional capacity primarily leads to greater thermal losses, which needs to be compensated by purchasing additional electricity, ultimately increasing the overall OPEX. The same trend can be observed in the 10 MW_e case. In both examples, the storage duration (capacity-to-power ratio of the TES system) of 4 hours yields the lowest electricity-related OPEX and further increase to storage duration of 8 hours is not beneficial. Moreover, when full OPEX is considered, which differs from values presented in 13 primarily by including the capacity network fee (charged per MW of installed EH power), the trend observable in Fig. 13 reverses,

Figure 15: CZ: LCOH for different sizing configurations. Note: Axes show discrete sizing combinations with uniform spacing for visualization; numerical values are indicated on the tick labels.

Figure 16: DE: LCOH for different sizing configurations.

making the scenarios with the lowest EH power the most economically effective in terms of OPEX. This is illustrated in Fig. 14. As a result, similar pattern can be observed for the LCOH results, as depicted in Fig. 15 and 16. The heatmaps show that, for a given EH power, the optimal storage duration is 2–4 hours, in both CZ and DE market. The optimal sizing configuration for both markets yielded EH nominal power of 5 MW_e and TES capacity of 10 MWh_{th}. However, the configuration 5 MW_e and 20 MWh_{th} achieves comparable performance, with an LCOH increase of less than 1% higher.

Comparing the techno-economic KPIs in CZ and DE markets, the lower-priced and more volatile DE market results in lower energy-dependent OPEX. However, once the capacity-based network fee is included, the total OPEX becomes lower in the CZ market. The LCOH values for the 5 MW_e cases are comparable in both markets, but increase at higher installed capacities in DE market, primarily due to the impact of the capacity network fee.

6.2. DAM+AS Scenario

This section focuses on the results of the techno-economic analysis of the DAM+AS scenario. The operation of the proposed system is visualized in Fig. 17. In the selected 3-day period, 73% of the electricity was procured from the DAM, and the remaining 27% came from activated RE in the aFRR- balancing market. For example, on 15 May, it is evident that the system took advantage of the near-zero electricity prices on the DAM between 12 a.m. and 2 p.m.

Figure 17: Operation on the DAM and aFRR- market for chosen 3 days in May 2024. (DAM+AS Scenario, CZ, base case sizing)

Figure 18: CZ: Share of electricity procured via DAM vs activated RE for aFRR.

Figure 19: DE: Share of electricity procured via DAM vs activated RE for aFRR.

The dispatch optimization algorithm also avoided hours with high spikes in RE price, that occurred at 6 a.m. and 6 p.m..

The techno-economic KPIs for base case sizing are summarized in table 6. The data shows that the provision of ancillary services not only generates revenues, it also lowers the OPEX, because less electricity needs to be purchased on the DAM. This results in 42 % decrease in the LCOH value compared to the DAM scenario.

Figure 18 presents the share between electricity procured at DAM and aFRR activated RE for different sizing scenarios in CZ market. The figure shows that the amount of activated RE increases strongly with higher installed EH power, while TES capacity has only a small effect. This is because the system supplies a continuous heat load, so the TES is regularly discharged, which continuously creates storage headroom for aFRR activation. As a result, the system is mainly limited by EH power rather than by TES capacity. Figure 18 also shows another interesting trend: the share of activated RE actually decreases in cases with the largest TES capacity (for the same installed EH power). This occurs because larger TES systems have higher thermal losses (given the modular

design assumption adopted in this study), which increases the total electricity required to meet the heat demand. Since the RE activation is already saturated, the additional electricity must be supplied from the DAM. Similar trends can be observed for the DE market represented in Fig. 19.

Next, the breakdown of OPEX, aFRR market revenues and the resulting NOC are presented in Fig.20. Regarding OPEX, DAM costs as well as the energy-dependent network charges decrease with increasing installed EH power of the P2H system, while capacity-dependent network fees increase. As a result, total OPEX decreases when EH power rises from 5 MW_e to 10 MW_e but increases for 20 MW_e. A similar pattern is observed with TES capacity, where total OPEX reductions occur up to a certain TES size, beyond which the OPEX rises again, due to having to cover more losses from a higher number of TES tanks as well as higher value of CAPEX-related OPEX, namely O&M costs and replacement costs. These OPEX trends are consistent for both CZ and DE markets. Regarding revenues, total aFRR-market revenue increases with both higher installed EH power and larger TES capacity in the CZ market. In contrast,

Figure 20: Net Operational Costs: OPEX and Revenues structure for different sizing.

Figure 21: CZ: LCOH for different sizing configurations.

Figure 22: DE: LCOH for different sizing configurations.

a different behavior is observed in the DE market, where revenues for activated RE in aFRR- market are negative, indicating payment from the BSP to the TSO, and thus representing an additional cost component. Capacity revenues remain positive and dominate the overall balance, resulting in positive total revenues from aFRR- services provision. It should be noted that in Fig. 20, costs are shown as positive values and revenues as negative values, consistent with the cost-minimization framework adopted in the dispatch optimization. Finally, the net operational cost, defined as total OPEX minus total revenue, is shown. A clear pattern emerges, with NOC consistently lower in the CZ market than in the DE market, highlighting the impact of market-specific conditions on system economics. Across all studied cases, total OPEX is lower and total revenue is higher in the CZ market compared to the DE market.

Next, the optimal sizing configuration is determined based on the LCOH value. Fig. 21 and Fig. 22 depict the LCOH for different sizing scenarios in CZ and DE markets. In the DAM scenario, the smallest configuration is preferred. In contrast, in the DAM+AS scenario, larger configurations become more favorable. The optimal sizing configuration is 20 MW_e and 40 MWh_{th} for the CZ market, and 20 MW_e and 80 MWh_{th} for the DE market. For a given EH power, the

optimal storage duration is 2–4 hours in both markets. This pattern is observed in the DAM scenario and remains valid when ancillary services (DAM+AS) are included. Some LCOH values in the CZ market are negative, reflecting cases where revenues from providing ancillary services exceed total lifetime costs. In this context, negative LCOH indicates a net economic benefit rather than a negative price for heat.

To summarize the results of the DAM+AS scenario, providing aFRR- services significantly improves the system's economic feasibility. The participation on balancing market not only generates additional revenue but also reduces OPEX by decreasing the amount of electricity that must be purchased on the DAM. As a result, the LCOH values are lower for all studied sizing cases compared to DAM only scenario. The reduction in LCOH is particularly pronounced in the CZ market, highlighting country-specific market conditions and underlining the importance of evaluating each market individually.

6.3. Comparison with conventional technologies

In this section, the proposed P2H+TES system is benchmarked against a conventional industrial steam generation technology, namely an electric boiler. The comparison is performed using two previously defined KPIs: Net Operational

Figure 23: DAM Scenario: Electricity cost savings (energy-dependent fees only)

Benefit (NOB) and annual CO₂ savings. Annual emissions in tonnes of CO₂ equivalent are expressed as percentages relative to the emissions of the EB scenario.

Comparing EB and DAM scenario, where neither of the systems generates revenue from participation in balancing markets, the NOB can be interpreted as OPEX savings. If only energy-dependent OPEX components (DAM costs and energy-dependent network charges) are considered, the DAM scenario results in OPEX savings that increase with higher installed EH power and higher TES capacity. However, when the full OPEX is considered, which mainly includes the addition of the capacity-based network fee, the trend changes. Cases with higher installed EH power incur higher capacity network charges compared to the EB scenario (with 5 MWe installed power). As a result, some configurations (e.g., all 20 MWe cases) exhibit higher total OPEX than the EB, reflected by negative OPEX savings. For a given EH installed power, the highest OPEX savings are achieved with an optimal storage duration of 2–4 hours, consistent with the results for minimum LCOH.

Figure 25 shows the CO₂ savings. Given the high EB efficiency, the proposed system yields higher annual CO₂ emissions in some sizing cases, reflected by negative CO₂ savings. This figure highlights the differences in grid emission factors between CZ and DE markets. It is evident that in DE, periods of higher renewable energy penetration correspond to lower electricity prices, which the dispatch optimizer selects for charging. As a result, configurations with larger TES capacities in DE zone achieve substantial CO₂ savings.

Next, the DAM+AS scenario is benchmarked against EB scenario. Figure 26 depicts the NOB for different sizing cases. The revenues generated from participation in balancing markets result in high NOB compared to EB scenario. Due to the capacity-based network fee, the highest NOB are not reached for the highest installed EH power, but for the 10 MWe and 40 MWh_{th} case in both CZ and DE markets. This suggest optimal storage duration of 4 hours, consistent with previous findings.

The CO₂ emissions generated in DAM+AS scenario are higher than EB scenario emissions in all studied cases,

Figure 24: DAM Scenario: OPEX savings

Figure 25: DAM Scenario: emission savings

Figure 26: DAM+AS Scenario: NOB

mainly due to EB's high efficiency. This is reflected in Fig. 27, that shows only negative CO₂ savings. These findings suggest that the times of favorable RE prices on the aFRR-market are not well aligned with times of low grid emission factor (high RES penetration).

7. Conclusion

This paper presented a comprehensive techno-economic assessment of a P2H system coupled with TES for industrial steam production. A MILP algorithm was developed to optimize system dispatch under dynamic electricity pricing,

Figure 27: DAM+AS Scenario: emission savings

considering participation in both the DAM and the aFRR-market. The analysis was conducted for two electricity markets, namely the Czech (CZ) and German (DE) markets, in order to assess the impact of different market characteristics. In addition, multiple system configurations were evaluated to determine the optimal system sizing. Finally, to assess the demand-side flexibility benefits provided by TES, the proposed P2H+TES system was benchmarked against a conventional P2H system, represented by an electric boiler. The main criteria for the techno-economic viability assessment included the levelized cost of heat (LCOH), operational expenditure (OPEX), revenues from balancing markets (REV), net operational costs (NOC), and net operational benefit (NOB) compared to the conventional solution. Based on the analysis conducted, the following conclusions can be stated.

The results demonstrate that participation in the aFRR-market significantly improves the economic performance of the proposed P2H+TES system. In the DAM-only scenario, an LCOH of 131 €/MWh was obtained. Compared to the DAM-only scenario, combined operation on the DAM and aFRR- market generates additional revenues while simultaneously reducing the amount of electricity that must be purchased on the DAM, resulting in lower OPEX and LCOH across all investigated system configurations. Market-specific conditions strongly influence system profitability, with the higher-priced CZ market showing more favorable economics than the more volatile DE market. For the optimally sized configuration under combined DAM+aFRR operation, LCOH values of 42 €/MWh were obtained for the DE market, while in the CZ market the LCOH reached -12 €/MWh. In this context, the negative LCOH indicates that revenues from ancillary services exceed total lifetime costs, implying a net economic benefit rather than a negative heat price.

The analysis further shows that regulated electricity network fees have a non-negligible impact on system economics and sizing decisions. In the DAM-only scenario, capacity-dependent network charges significantly increase OPEX and therefore favor smaller installed electric heater capacities. However, when participation in the aFRR- market is considered, higher revenues compensate for these additional costs, making larger installed capacities economically viable.

The results also reveal that, for a given electric heater capacity, the optimal TES capacity corresponds to a storage duration of approximately 2–4 hours, a pattern that remains consistent across all studied scenarios, although this result is specific to the industrial heat demand profile considered. In addition, the system's provision of balancing energy is primarily limited by the installed electric heater power rather than by TES capacity, as the continuous industrial heat demand regularly discharges the storage and maintains sufficient headroom for reserve activation.

When benchmarked against a conventional P2H solution, an electric boiler, the proposed P2H+TES configuration demonstrates clear economic advantages, achieving reductions in operational costs, with savings of up to 0.275 M€/y in the DAM-only scenario and significant reductions of 0.9–1.9 M€/y when participation in the aFRR- market is included.

This study highlights the potential of P2H+TES systems to provide negative automatic frequency restoration reserve. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first techno-economic assessment investigating the participation of such systems in balancing markets for industrial steam supply. The results show that providing aFRR can significantly improve the business case of the system while simultaneously contributing to grid stability. Future research should further explore the techno-economic potential of P2H+TES systems in providing additional ancillary services, including other frequency control and balancing services. Such analyses could support the integration of P2H+TES technologies that can help decarbonize industrial heat while providing guidance for industrial stakeholders.

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A. Appendix

A.1. Thermal loss estimation input data

Input data for thermal loss estimation are summarized in Table 7. The thermophysical properties of YARA MOST can be found in [34]. Air properties were obtained from REFPROP.

A.2. Electricity network tariff charges

Electricity network charges considered in this study for CZ [48] and DE [49] market are described in Table 8. These regulated charges apply to industrial off-takers connected at the very high voltage level.

Table 7

Input data for thermal loss calculation from TES tanks (base case scenario)

Parameter	Value	Unit
Tank diameter	3	m
Tank length	6.5	m
Minimum MS height	0.25	m
Minimum air height	0.25	m
Hot tank operational temperature	480	°C
Cold tank operational temperature	180	°C
Ambient temperature	20	°C
Wall thickness	8	mm
Insulation thickness	200	mm
Wall thermal conductivity	20	W/(m K)
Insulation conductivity	0.12	W/(m K)
Outside air heat transfer coefficient	5	W/(m ² K)
Safety factor SF	1.5	[-]

Table 8

Regulated electricity network charges in CZ and DE markets

Component	Unit	CZ	DE
Capacity-based network charge	€/MW/month	4 382	7 633
Energy-dependent network charges			
Transmission network tariff	€/MWh	1.8	13.2
System services charge	€/MWh	6.8	*
Electricity surcharges	€/MWh	19.8	13.3

*included in the variable network charge

1 EUR ≈ 25 CZK is assumed.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pavla Lukášová: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. **Adam Kubín:** Methodology, Software, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Radek Procházka:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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